

Classical Frequencies in Quantum Mechanics?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 10, 2019

In this brief note, we investigate the role of classical frequencies in quantum mechanical problems. It is known through the correspondence principle that quantum mechanics matches classical physics for high energy levels. It has been shown in previous notes, however, that classical features are already present in all quantum energy levels as the Schrodinger equation may be written as: $(-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx W(x)] / W(x) = .5m v(x)v(x) = E-V(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. Thus, if there is periodic behaviour associated with $v(x)$, as in an oscillator, it should carry through into the quantum average kinetic energy and potential energy and finally into E , the average energy. This also suggests that the f_p 's ($W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \text{ } f_p \exp(ipx)$) are influenced by the classical frequency w .

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The time-independent Schrodinger equation may be written as:

$$[\sum \text{over } p \text{ } p^2/2m f_p \exp(ipx)] / W(x) = .5 m v(x)v(x) \quad ((1))$$

Here $v(x)$ is the classical velocity at point x , so the sum over all p 's from minus infinite to infinite multiplied by $p^2/2m$ and $P(p/x) = f_p \exp(ipx)/W(x)$, $W(x)$ is a normalization constant (the wavefunction) is linked directly to classical kinetic energy for any energy level. If $v(x)$ is periodic, it seems this should affect f_p as well as the average kinetic energy and potential energy. The sum of average kinetic and potential energy should equal the total classical energy, or the average quantum energy.

Consider the classical case of an oscillator.

$$v(x) = v_0 \sin(\omega t) \text{ where } \omega \text{ is the angular frequency and } .5k A^2 = .5m v_0^2 \quad ((2))$$

Here A is the amplitude of the spring and $\omega = \sqrt{k/m}$. This suggests that:

$$v(x) = \omega A \sin(\omega t) \quad ((3))$$

The average kinetic energy is:

$$\int dx \text{ } .5 m \omega^2 A^2 \sin^2(\omega t) (1/\omega) \omega dt = \int dp \text{ } p^2/2m f_p^2 \quad (\text{one dimension}) \quad ((4))$$

This suggests the average kinetic energy goes as w as ωt is an angle and the first integral is over the angular period of the sine function. It also suggests that $f_p(\omega)$. For the ground state, f_p

is related to $\exp(-p^2/(2mE))$ and the integral on the right should be of the form $\frac{1}{2} E$. Thus, E should also go as ω for the ground state.

For the classical oscillator, the potential energy is $\frac{1}{2} k x(t)x(t) = \frac{1}{2} k A^2 \cos(\omega t)\cos(\omega t)$. If one uses $(k/m) = \omega^2$, this is equal to $\frac{1}{2} \omega^2 A^2 \cos^2(\omega t)$ and:

$$\text{Average potential energy (classical)} = \frac{1}{2} \omega^2 A^2 \int_0^{2\pi} \cos^2(\omega t) \frac{1}{2\pi} d(\omega t)$$

Thus, average potential energy and hence E goes as ω^2 for a classical oscillator. For quantum mechanics, the density is $W(x)W(x)$ so:

$$\int dx W(x)W(x) \left(-\frac{1}{2m}\right) \left[\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x)\right]/W(x) + \int dx W(x)W(x) V(x) = E \quad ((5))$$

The first term is the average kinetic energy and the second, average potential. One may write the average kinetic energy as:

$\int dx W(x)W(x) [E - V(x)]$ suggesting that both E and average potential energy may be proportional to ω . For a classical oscillator, the average kinetic energy equals the average potential energy. For the quantum oscillator case:

$$\text{Average KE} = \sum p \frac{p^2}{2m} f_p f_p \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Average } V(x) = \int dx \frac{1}{2} k x^2 W(x)W(x)$$

For all states of the quantum oscillator, f_p and $W(x)$ are of the same functional form. (Note: for the ground state $W(x)$ goes as $\exp(-mEx^2)$ while f_p goes as $\exp(-p^2/(2mE))$ and this factor is included in higher states.)

Thus, it seems that classical frequency ω affects quantum mechanics. In the case of the quantum oscillator, we have E proportional to ω . The full quantum solution gives $E = \hbar \omega (n + \frac{1}{2})$.

Particle in a Box with an Infinite Potential at the Walls

Consider the case of a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. In the classical case, the particle bounces back and forth with a frequency f related to $2L = v (1/f)$. This suggests the classical energy $\frac{1}{2} m v^2 = \frac{1}{2} m (2L f)^2$. The quantum solution is of the form $\sin(kx-b)$ where k is the root mean square momentum related to the average energy $(\hbar k)^2/2m$, so k should be linked to a classical frequency.

Cycling

It has been argued in a previous note (1), that one may write the time independent Schrodinger equation with $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ expressed as Fourier series. This leads to:

$$p^2/2m f_p + \sum_{j+k=p} V_j f_k = E f_p \quad ((6))$$

It was suggested this implies a cycling is occurring for each f_p . Different f_k 's scatter off the potential $V(x)$ to create an f_p . The right hand side of ((6)) suggests one may have a time dependence of $\exp(iEt)$. Thus, there is the same time dependence for each f_p . We have argued in this note, that E may be proportional to w , the mechanical frequency in the problem, as in the oscillator case. In quantum mechanics:

$$\text{Average KE} = \sum \overline{p^2} / 2m \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Average PE} = \sum \overline{V_j} \quad \text{((7))}$$

Thus, the cycling seems to be associated largely with the potential energy as plane waves scatter from one state into another to form a resonance with a cycling frequency of $1/E$. For the oscillator $E = \hbar \omega (n + .5)$ so as n increases, E is close to a multiple of w and $1/E$ becomes smaller and smaller than $1/w$, the classical frequency.

In a previous note (2), it was argued that if a plane wave, with momentum k , interacts with a potential $V(x)$ written as a Fourier series, there should be a certain probability for it to collide with V_j , the j th Fourier transform. Given that the momentum from the collision will be $k+j$, one will obtain f_{k+j} , thus this may be related to the relative probability. In fact, given that V_j carries energy information, one may argue that $\sum_{j+k=p} V_j f_k = \text{constant} f_p$ where $\text{constant} = E$. Thus, different f_k 's may interact with different V_j 's to always form f_p , namely: $\sum_{j+k=p} V_j f_k$. It is not only the case that one obtains $E f_p$ on the right hand side of ((6)), it seems the interactions between the f_k 's and V_j 's, must take place over the same cycle time $1/E$ for a quantum bound state resonance to exist.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems that by writing the Schrodinger equation as ((1)) and linking it to $.5 m v(x)v(x)$, where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity at x , classical periodicities in $v(x)$, such as in the oscillator case, influence the quantum mechanical solution. In particular, E may be proportional to w (as well as average quantum KE and PE) and f_p and $W(x)$, the wavefunction are also influenced.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. 2x2 Matrix Model and the Schrodinger Equation (preprint, zenodo, 2018)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Role of Average Energy and Plane Waves in the Schrodinger Equation (preprint, zenodo, 2019)